

Solution properties of cationic and anionic surfactants : effect of solvents and polymers

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The solution properties of one cationic [cetyltrimethylammonium bromide] and one anionic [sodium dodecyl sulphate] surfactants in water in the presence of methanol, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide, ethylene-glycol and different polymers (polyethylene glycol-600 and 20000) have been investigated. The critical micelle concentration (CMC), and the degree of dissociation of the micelle (β) were determined by conductometric method. These micellar parameters of both the surfactants show a significant dependence on the solvents as well as on the number of repeating units of glycol oligomers.

Micellar properties of both anionic and cationic surfactants are significantly influenced by the presence of additives¹. They provide vital information about the solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions in surfactant solutions, and hence, have lead to extensive structural, kinetic and thermodynamic studies. The properties of surfactant solutions can be effectively tuned to a desired range and application by altering (i) the tendency to form micelles, as reflected by the CMC, and (ii) the structure and shape of the micelles by changing the additive conditions.

Table 1. Values of CMC and β (degree of counterion dissociation) of surfactants in various solvent systems by the conductometric method

Temp. = 27°C

Solvents	vol/vol (%)	CMC $\times 10^3/\text{mol dm}^{-3}$		β	
		CTAB	SDS	CTAB	SDS
MeOH	0	0.99	7.90	0.29	0.30
	10	1.80	12.1	0.32	0.44
	50	3.00	25.0	0.41	0.71
CH ₃ CN	10	1.90	20.0	0.43	0.39
	50	3.80	40.0	0.45	0.83
DMF	10	2.50	15.0	0.51	0.77
	50	7.00	30.0	0.61	0.77
Ethylene glycol	10	1.40	10.0	0.34	0.33
	25	2.71	14.5	0.40	0.45
	50	4.80	23.5	0.51	0.59

In the present study, two types of additives, viz. solvent and polymer have been used. From the conductivity data, the CMC and the counterion dissociation constant of the cationic (CTAB) and anionic (SDS) surfactants have been determined in the binary mixtures of ethylene glycol (EG-H₂O), dimethylformamide (DMF-H₂O), methanol (MeOH-

H₂O) and acetonitrile (ACN-H₂O), and non-ionic polymers like polyethylene glycol (mol. wt. 600 and 20000). Recently polymer-surfactant systems are under extensive investigation² due to their wide industrial applications. Moreover, the additive effect of repeating units will affect the nature of interactions responsible for micelle formation. A major question that remains to be solved in order to fully understand polymer-micelle interaction is the role of surfactant charge on the tendency to associate with polymers.

Results and discussion

The specific conductivity is linearly related to the surfactant concentration in both the pre-micellar and post-micellar regions. A break in the plot of specific conductance versus surfactant concentration indicates micelle formation (CMC) and the ratio of the slopes of this plot in post-micellar region to that in the pre-micellar region gives the degree of counterion dissociation, β . The values of CMC and β in

Fig. 1. Plots of [CTAB] in polymers (10% v/v) vs κ : (O) water, (■) PEG-600, (Δ) PEG-20000.

various solvents are given in Table 1. Some typical plots of the conductance data from which the CMC and β were derived are shown in Figs. 1–3. It is seen from Table 1 that the CMC of CTAB and SDS surfactants increases with increasing composition of solvents. Our observation can be explained in terms of the two interactions responsible for the micellization, i.e. hydrophobic interactions and the break up of the water structure. Generally the structure of water of liquid water is considered in terms of three-dimensional hydrogen bonded "flickering clusters" which retain much of the ordered structure of ice. Surfactant monomers with a long hydrocarbon chain increase the orderliness of water by formation of "Frank-Evan iceberg" around the hydrocarbon chain, resulting in a decrease in the entropy of the system. However, aggregation of the amphiphile monomer by formation of spherical micelles (due to hydrophobic interaction) breaks the icebergs and thereby increases the entropy; therefore hydrophobic interaction is an entropy directed process. Addition of solvents decreases the polarity (lowers the dielectric constant) of the medium as a result of which the hydrophobicity of the hydrocarbon tails decreases. Hence, the CMC is observed at a higher concentration of surfactant.

Table 2. Values of CMC and β (degree of counterion dissociation) of surfactants in polymer systems by the conductometric method

temp. = 27°C					
Additives	vol/vol (%)	CMC $\times 10^3 / \text{mol dm}^{-3}$		β	
		CTAB	SDS	CTAB	SDS
PEG-600	10	1.52	10.0	0.28	0.67
	20	2.31	–	0.29	–
	40	4.80	–	0.46	–
	50	7.00	20.0	0.81	0.71
PEG-20000	10	1.40	9.10	0.37	0.40
	20	1.82	–	0.44	–
	40	2.30	–	0.59	–
	50	2.50	13.0	0.71	0.46

CMC in EG and PEG-H₂O mixtures :

Ethylene glycol is one of the weakest organic denaturants and is also highly associative solvents³. The molecule is small and forms hydrogen bonded networks having mainly two-dimensional cooperative domains. The CMC values of CTAB and SDS increase non-linearly with increasing concentration of EG (Fig. 2, Table 1). The degree of counterion-binding, also decreases regularly in each case. The above result can be explained on the basis of structure breaking properties of EG, which may disturb the dissolved hydrophobic group, causing increase of CMC. On

Fig. 2. Plots of [CTAB, 10% v/v] in ethylene glycol vs K : (O) water, (■) 10% (v/v), (Δ) 50% (v/v).

the other hand the preferential solvation of EG, which results in the association of spherical micelles in order to form the rod-like micelles may also be responsible for the increase of CMC. A decrease in the dielectric constant of the aqueous phase would result in an increase in the repulsion between the ionic head groups, leading to a delayed micellization. The formation of pre-aggregates before the CMC would also increase the CMC.

Fig. 3. Plots of [SDS in CH₃CN] vs K : (O) water, (■) 10% (v/v), (Δ) 50% (v/v).

It can be observed from Table 2 that both PEG-600 and PEG-20000 increase the CMC of CTAB and SDS at all concentration levels studied. The quantitative modeling of polymer/surfactant mixture is most difficult problem. The dimensions of the surfactant micelles are normally small compared to the radius of gyration of the polymer, but they are large compared to the polymer thickness. The additives PEG-600 and 20000 form hydrogen bonds with water molecules. The favourable hydrogen bonding ability of these additives lead to poorer contribution to the hydrophobic interactions, which is driving force for micellization, and hence the higher CMC values. The increase in the number of repeating units does not have any significant influence on the CMC.

Experimental

The surfactants and polymers were products of Aldrich/Fluka and were used without further purification. Surfactant solutions of a definite concentration were always freshly prepared by weighing out a certain amount of surfactant and diluting it upto the required volume with double distilled water. Methanol (CH₃OH), dimethyl formamide (DMF), ethylene glycol (EG) and acetonitrile (CH₃CN) from Qualigens were used. The conductance measurements were carried out with a Systronics digital conductometer (Type 304).

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